

Studies on Hydroxamic Acids: Part VI. Thermodynamic Stability Constants of Beryllium (II) and N-Phenylbenzohydroxamic Acid Complexes

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The thermodynamic stability constants of beryllium (II) and N-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid complexes in 50 volume percent dioxan-water medium at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ have been determined by pH titration.

The mean activity co-efficient for uni-univalent electrolyte, computed from Harned and Owen's data in 50% dioxan-water medium at different ionic strengths, are used in the evaluation of thermodynamic constants. It is observed that in the range of ionic strength ~ 0 to $0.1 M$, the calculation procedure adapted here and the activity co-efficient correction terms are justified because the thermodynamic stability constants are found to be independent of the ionic strength and metal to ligand ratio.

Relatively little work has been done on the determination of the stability constants of metal complexes of hydroxamic acids. A few systems have been worked out with N-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid¹⁻⁶. No reference could, however, be traced out in literature on the study of stability constants of beryllium (II) and hydroxamic acid complexes. In this communication the thermodynamic stability constants of the complexes of beryllium (II) with N-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid (PBHA) are reported and discussed.

The metal-ligand stability constants are most conveniently determined by potentiometric Calvin-Bjerrum⁷ titration technique. The procedure for calculations used here, combines the method of Van Uitert⁸⁻⁹ and Block and Mc Intyre¹⁰ with subsequent modification of Goldberg.¹¹ In the present study the thermodynamic stability constants, which are independent of the ionic strength, can be evaluated by applying the mean activity coefficient corrections to the concentration stability constants.

EXPERIMENTAL

Calibration of Glass Electrode: During the present investigation 50 volume percent aqueous-dioxan is employed as the solvent medium, because both N-phenylbenzohydroxamic

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acid and its beryllium complexes are practically insoluble in aqueous medium. To make pH meter readings meaningful in aqueous-dioxan medium, Van Uitert *et al.*⁸⁻⁹, applied empirical corrections. According to their treatment the glass electrode can be calibrated to measure the stoichiometric hydrogen ion concentration, $[H^+]$, from the meter reading, B , in aqueous-dioxan media by the relation

$$-\log [H^+] = B + \log U_H \quad \dots (1)$$

where

$$\log U_H = \log U_H^0 - \log \frac{1}{\gamma_{\pm}} \quad \dots (2)$$

or

$$-\log [H^+] = B + \log U_H^0 - \log \frac{1}{\gamma_{\pm}} \quad \dots (3)$$

The correction factor U_H^0 is independent of the ionic concentration but is dependent on the composition and the temperature of the solvent. The value of $\log U_H^0$ for 50% v/v dioxan-water is 0.24 at 35°. The mean activity coefficients, γ_{\pm} , of the monovalent electrolyte at particular ionic strength and solvent composition have been interpolated from the data of Harned and Owen¹³ on hydrochloric acid.

Chemicals and Apparatus: All the chemicals used were of Analar or G.R. grade of B.D.H. or E. Merck, respectively unless otherwise specified. Graduated apparatus of standard calibration was used.

Purification and Testing of Dioxan: B.D.H. 'Analar' dioxan was purified by Weissberger's method¹⁴. The purity was ascertained by determining the freezing point which was found to be 11.6 to 11.9° against the reported value¹⁴ of 11.65–12.00°.

Carbonate Free KOH: Carbonate free KOH was prepared by the electrolysis of A.R. KCl, as recommended for the preparation of carbonate free NaOH from NaCl¹⁵. The absence of carbonate in KOH solution was tested with BaCl₂ solution¹⁶.

0.1 M KOH solution was prepared in 50 volume percent dioxan-water. This solution gave negative test for carbonate.

Carbonate Free Water: The absence of carbonate in glass distilled water was tested according to the method of Kolthoff and Sandell¹⁷.

Preparation of Beryllium (II) solution: Beryllium (II) solution was prepared by dissolving about 24.6 gms. of Be(NO₃)₂·3H₂O (Russian) in 130 ml. of 0.979 N HNO₃ and diluting

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with water to 250 ml. Be(II) content of this solution was determined gravimetrically.¹⁸ It was 0.4918 *M* with respect to Be(II) and 0.5098 *M* with respect to HNO₃.

Preparation of the Ligand : PBHA was prepared by the modified method of Priyadarshini and Tandon¹⁹. It was recrystallized from hot benzene before use and was vacuum dried; m.p., found 121°, reported 121°.¹⁹

Standardization of pH meter : Battery operated Radiometer pH meter Model 4C PHM No. 64570 (Denmark), with a general purpose unshielded glass electrode, G 200 B, and saturated calomel electrode, K 100, was used for pH measurements. The instrument was calibrated into 0.01 units of pH.

The titrations were performed at 35° ± 0.1° under an atmosphere of pure nitrogen. The loss of solvent due to evaporation consequent to bubbling of nitrogen was compensated by passing the purified nitrogen through 50% dioxan-water mixture before bubbling it through the titration solution. The pH meter was standardized with different buffers²⁰ namely, with saturated solution of potassium hydrogentartrate (pH 3.56), 0.05 *M* potassium hydrogen phthalate (pH 4.02) and 0.01 *M* borax (pH 9.10).

Titration Procedure : A specially designed three necked titration vessel, accommodating a microburette (2 × 0.01 ml), a saturated KCl salt bridge and a glass electrode, and having an arrangement for bubbling nitrogen into the solution, was used. In this vessel 0.5 millimoles of PBHA, 25 ml of dioxan, 10 ml of 0.004918 *M* beryllium (II) nitrate (0.005098 *M* w.r.t. HNO₃) and 15 ml of water were taken. The total volume of the solution was taken to be 50 ml, neglecting error of contraction during mixing.

Final concentrations of Be(II), PBHA and HNO₃ were generally around 0.001 *M*, 0.01 *M* and 0.001 *M*, respectively.

The contents of the titration vessel were thermostated and purged with nitrogen for about 20–25 minutes. Titration was carried out by adding a small volume of 0.1 *M* KOH (50% dioxan-water v/v) each time and noting the highest pH.

In titrations involving adjustment of ionic strength, weighed amount of salts such as KCl, KClO₄, NaClO₄ and KNO₃ were added directly to the titration vessel. The metalligand ratio in the above titrations was generally 1 : 10 although studies at other ratios were also made.

CALCULATIONS

The method of calculations adopted here is basically due to Goldberg¹¹. PBHA, represented here as HCh, ionises as under :—

$$\text{Hence } K_a = \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{Ch}^-]}{[\text{HCh}]}, \quad \frac{\gamma_{\text{H}^+} \cdot \gamma_{\text{Ch}^-}}{\gamma_{\text{HCh}}} = \frac{(\gamma_{\pm})^2}{q_{\text{H}}}$$

$$pK_a = \log q_{\text{H}} + 2 \log 1/\gamma_{\pm} \quad \dots (4)$$

18. Ref. 15, p. 517.

19. U. Priyadarshini and S. G. Tandon, *J. Chem. Eng. Data.*, 1967, **12**, 143.

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For the divalent metal ion M^{2+} , the metal-ligand reactions are

The formation constants are defined as

$$K_1 = \frac{[MCh^+]}{[M^{2+}][Ch^-]} \cdot \frac{\gamma MCh^+}{\gamma M^{2+} \cdot \gamma Ch^-} = \frac{q_1}{(\gamma_{\pm})^4} \quad (5)$$

$$K_2 = \frac{[MCh_2]}{[MCh^+][Ch^-]} \cdot \frac{\gamma MCh_2}{\gamma MCh^+ \cdot \gamma Ch^-} = \frac{q_2}{(\gamma_{\pm})^2} \quad (6)$$

In the derivation of the above equations, it is assumed that the activity co-efficients of the natural species are unity and those of unipositive and uninegative ions are approximately equal to the mean activity co-efficient, γ_{\pm} . Besides, it is assumed that $\gamma_{\pm}(2:1) = \gamma^4_{\pm}(1:1)$, where $\gamma_{\pm}(2:1)$ and $\gamma_{\pm}(1:1)$ are the mean activity co-efficients of bi-univalent and uni-univalent electrolytes, respectively.

The concentration of the free chelating agent, $[Ch^-]$ may be evaluated from the following equation:—

$$[Ch^-] = \frac{ChCh + ChNO_3 - CoH - [H^+] + [OH^-]}{qH \cdot [H^+]} \quad \dots (7)$$

The quantity, \bar{n} , the available number of ligands bound per metal ion, may be determined as follows:—

$$\bar{n} = \frac{ChCh - (qH \cdot [H^+] + 1)[Ch^-]}{\cdot C_M} \quad \dots (8)$$

The hydrogen ion concentration as required in equations 7 and 8, is obtained from the equation 3.

The mean molarity of ions in terms of monovalent electrolyte, m_{\pm} , during the first and the second steps of coordination reactions is given by the equations¹³ 9 and 10, respectively.

$$m_{\pm} = 1.59 (C_M - C_{OH}) + 2C_{OH} + C_{HNO_3} \quad \dots (9)$$

$$m_{\pm} = 2C_M + C_{HNO_3} \quad \dots (10)$$

Using the values of \bar{n} and corresponding values of $[Ch^-]$, the molarity quotients q_1 and q_2 are evaluated by the method of Block and Mc Intyre.¹⁰

$$J_1 = (1 - \bar{n}) [Ch^-] \quad \dots (11)$$

$$J_2 = (2 - \bar{n}) [Ch^-]^2 \quad \dots (12)$$

$$J'_1 = (1 - \bar{n}') [Ch'^-] \quad \dots (13)$$

$$J'_2 = (2 - \bar{n}') [Ch'^-]^2 \quad \dots (14)$$

The symbols have been defined.¹⁰

$$q_1 = \frac{\bar{n} J'_2 - \bar{n}' J_2}{J_1 J'_2 - J'_1 J_2} \quad \dots (15)$$

$$q_2 = \frac{\bar{n}' J_1 - \bar{n} J'_1}{\bar{n} J'_2 - \bar{n}' J_2} \quad \dots (16)$$

The stepwise thermodynamic stability constants can be evaluated from the concentration constants as under :—

$$\log K_1 = \log q_1 + 4 \log 1/\gamma_{\pm} \quad \dots (17)$$

$$\log K_2 = \log q_2 + 2 \log 1/\gamma_{\pm} \quad \dots (18)$$

The overall stability constant, $\log \beta_2$ is given by

$$\log \beta_2 = \log K_1 + \log K_2 \quad \dots (19)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A large number of *pH* titrations were performed at different concentrations of reactants and by varying the metal to ligand ratio. Free nitric acid added to the beryllium(II) stock solution checked the formation of any hydrolytic precipitation in it and also served to suppress the complexation reaction. Experimental observations for a typical titration in 50 volume percent dioxan at 35° are recorded in Table 1. The *pK_a* of PBHA under these

TABLE I

Beryllium (II)—PBHA Titration Data at 35° in 50% v/v Aqueous/Dioxan Medium

Be²⁺ = 0.9836 mM; PBHA = 13.01 mM;

HNO₃ = 10.20 mM; KNO₃ = 8.11 mM.

Ionic Strength = 0.01 *M*

KOH 0.1003 <i>M</i>	B	[Ch ⁻] × 10 ⁺⁹	\bar{n}
0.00	2.90	—	—
0.20	3.10	4.4630	0.0714
0.40	3.50	2.512	0.175
0.50	3.80	—	—
0.65	4.20	5.635	0.3501*
0.70	4.30	7.036	0.4432†
0.73	4.40	8.816	0.4950
0.76	4.45	9.845	0.5469
0.90	4.75	19.14	0.8484
1.10	5.25	44.67	1.050
1.15	5.40	81.81	1.320
1.20	5.60	128.5	1.416†
1.25	5.80	201.8	1.546*
1.30	6.10	397.8	1.610
1.40	7.10	944.1	1.750
1.45	8.50	3928.0	1.828

* From these values $\log K_1 = 8.65$;

$\log K_2 = 7.20$

† From these values $\log K_1 = 8.70$;

$\log K_2 = 7.14$.

conditions was 10.96^{12} . The values of the formation function, \bar{n} , and the concentration of the free chelating agent, $[\text{Ch}^-]$, were determined by the calculation procedure described earlier. The data, thus obtained, were used for plotting the formation curve (Fig. 1) and for evaluating the formation constants. In Table II the chelate formation constants have been recorded. Since activity co-efficient corrections have been applied, the equilibrium constants are thermodynamic constants. The maximum scatter was ± 0.20 in $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ or $\log K_1K_2$.

From the formation curve it is unambiguously inferred that the penta and hexa coordinated complexes are not formed. Maximum complexation involved is the four coordinated species with $\text{Be}^{2+} : \text{PBHA} :: 1 : 2$. Shome²¹ obtained the $\text{Be}(\text{II})-\text{PBHA}$ complex in the form of white granular substance and used it for the gravimetric determination of metal in the pH range 5.5 to 6.5. In the solid complex $\text{Be}(\text{II}) : \text{PBHA}$ was 1 : 2. Thus it is noticed that both in the solution and solid state the complex can be represented as under :

In the determination of the metal-ligand stability constants, errors are incorporated due to the anion complexation and metal ion hydrolysis. The data given in Table II show that the anions nitrate, chloride and perchlorate have no influence on the stability constants under the experimental conditions. Likewise, hydrolysis of $\text{Be}(\text{II})$ caused negligible error in the values of stability constants. The pH of hydrolysis for $\text{Be}(\text{II})$ is 5.7 in aqueous medium at 25° .²² Hence the stability constants were calculated by using the titration data below the pH of hydrolysis; assuming that the "B" of hydrolysis under the experimental conditions will also be in the vicinity of 5.7.

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TABLE II

Stability Constants of Be(II)-PBHA Complexes at 35° in 50% v/v Dioxan-Water

Electrolyte added	Ionic Strength	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂
Nil	0.005	8.68	7.15	15.83*
KNO ₃	0.01	8.70	7.14	15.84
"	0.016	8.74	7.12	15.86
"	0.05	8.88	7.13	16.01
"	0.10	8.77	7.11	15.88
KCl	0.01	8.70	7.18	15.88
"	0.02	8.75	7.11	15.86
"	0.05	8.85	7.16	16.01
"	0.10	8.83	7.00	15.83
KClO ₄	0.01	8.74	7.20	15.94
"	0.02	8.72	7.25	15.97
"	0.05	8.88	7.20	16.08
NaClO ₄	0.10	8.91	6.95	15.86†

* Average of 10 independent measurements.

† Used NaClO₄ to adjust μ = 0.10 M; KClO₄ could not be used because of its low solubility.

It is of interest to compare the stability constants of the complexes of PBHA with other bivalent metal ions. The data given in Table III are taken from the work of Shukla.¹²

TABLE III

Stability Constants of Bivalent Metal Complexes of PBHA.

	Cu(II)	Be(II)	Zn(II)	Ni(II)
log K ₁	10.36	8.68	7.51	7.00
log K ₂	8.78	7.15	6.63	5.91
log β ₂	19.14	15.83	14.14	12.91

The order of the stability constants is

This order is in good agreement with the work of Fernelius, Bryant and Douglas,²³ who have found out stability constants of bivalent metal ions with Tropolon and the order is

In general, this order agrees with that found for coordination compounds of ammonia, ethylenediamine, salicylaldehyde, 8-hydroxyquinolene etc. In short, the order is similar to that of Irving William's order.

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